

Youth Participation in Zimbabwean Electoral Processes

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Abstract

Youth participation in Zimbabwe's national elections has generally been characterized by violence and apathy. This has been a noticeable trend particularly in the post 2000 era. This paper provides an analysis of youth participation in electoral process as it exists in Zimbabwe. The paper discusses the level of youths' knowledge about political processes, the extent to which the youth in Zimbabwe are involved in the electoral processes and the challenges faced by youths in Zimbabwe during and after elections. The paper is based on a qualitative study done in Makokoba constituency located in Bulawayo Metropolitan Province. The study which is part of a growing body of research of youth and electoral participation was informed by the Rationale Choice Theory propounded by William Riker in 1962.

Keywords: Youth, Elections, participation, informed decision, electoral processes

Introduction

Youths are believed to be visionary, energetic, ingenious and idealistic in nature. Therefore, given an opportunity to fully express their opinions about the future, they can positively change the society they live in. The most democratic way to express one's opinion is through participating in elections without being influenced by others. Ensuring youth's participation in elections can be regarded as a solution to ending electoral violence. It can enhance sustainable peace and good governance in Zimbabwe and Africa at large. In most African states, however, the youths are manipulated during elections by politicians. The process of electoral manipulation amongst youths can be facilitated by flawed electoral processes. Therefore, this paper explores Zimbabwean electoral processes and the level of youth participation. The paper is based on a study carried out by the authors in Bulawayo's Makokoba constituency. The paper begins by giving a brief background of democratization in the world and Africa spearheaded by United Nations and regional bodies. The paper then highlights few conflicts that have rocked Zimbabwe since independence. The paper discusses the concept of electoral participation and outlining a theoretical framework that informed the Makokoba study. Research findings are presented and discussed in the last part of the paper.

Background to Youth Participation in Electoral Processes

Since the dawn of Pan-Africanism and anti-colonial movements in the 1950s, youths in Africa have been at the forefront of calling for radical change in the political and economic spheres that affect

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their lives. A notable example of youth sacrifice for their rights is the Soweto uprising of 1976 in South Africa. Most nationalist political movements started as youth organization movements and transformed into political and liberation movements. The youth of that era recognized the importance of political participation as a way of making their voices heard. Political participation typically refers to activities by citizens that are aimed at influencing the selection and decision of government personnel (Resnick and Daniela 2011). These activities include voting in elections, as well as more informal modes of engagement, such as meeting with community members, contacting political representatives, or involvement in collective action and civil society. The significance of youth participation in elections can be fully grasped in the context of democratization discourse.

The spread of democracy around the world has been seen as a major highway leading to democratization of governments and making possible the act of sovereignty envisaged in the United Nations Charter. The United Nations Organisation (UNO)'s history is interwoven with elections extending to the period shortly after its founding, when in the late 1940s, it observed elections on the Korean Peninsula (United Nations 2010). During the subsequent era of trusteeship and decolonisation, the UNO supervised and observed plebiscites, referenda and elections worldwide. Today, as the call for democratic change becomes louder in the Middle East and African regions and elsewhere, the UNO continues to be a trusted impartial actor. The United Nations continues to provide electoral assistance to a broad range of countries at the request of Member States or based on a Security Council or General Assembly mandate working with regional blocks, (United Nations 2010).

Africa has had a long journey with regard to establishing democracies, as many nations have suffered decades of autocratic rulers and repeated coups d'état. Recently, Africa has been at the forefront of a democratic revitalization, as many nations now welcome a free and open political system. The pattern of democracy is catching on throughout the continent, and the world is beginning to take notice. However, Santos (2005) notes that to retain a truly inclusive democratic society, everyone must be involved in the political process. In African nations, a large segment of the population remains marginalised, namely the youths. In other parts of the world, the youths have played a vital role in elections, but in Africa, institutional and policy constraints have hindered youth involvement in the democratic process (UNDP 2010). This trend is beginning to change, however as recent African elections have shown the crucial role that the youths can play in the political system.

Danielle and Daniela (2011) note that youth have long represented an important constituency for electoral mobilisation in Africa. Today, as the region faces a growing "youth bulge" that is disproportionately burdened by unemployment and underemployment electoral violence is rife. Sachikonye (2011) posits that votes of youths are becoming more important than ever before. Despite their numerical importance and the historical relevance of generational identities within the region, little is known about the political participation of Africa's youths in general and Zimbabwe in particular. Be that as it may, there are international and national frameworks which give impetus to youth participation in government and governance issues of their respective countries. Many countries are signatories to international conventions that promote youth participation.

In Zimbabwe, achieving sustainable peace has been a difficulty especially during and after elections. In 1983 political violence loomed in Matabeleland against dissidents in an operation known as "Gukurahundi" done by the North Korean trained 5th brigade, (Catholic Commission for Justice and Peace 1999). The government led by Robert Mugabe believed that the dissidents' aim was to overthrow him from power. The dissidents were former ZIPRA forces who had fought in the liberation war. CCJP (1999) notes that approximately two thousand civilians had been murdered and hundreds of households burned within a short space of time after the 5th brigade invaded Matabeleland and part of Midlands' province. In addition, violence erupted in late 1984 towards

elections as ZANU PF youths were attacking ZAPU supporters and forcing them to attend their rallies.

After the formation of the strong opposition party Movement for Democratic Change (MDC) in 1999, in the year 2000 Zimbabwe experienced an increase in cases of political violence in the run up to election (Sachikonye, 2011). Opposition supporters have been the main victims of the political violence. They were abducted, murdered and their households burned. During the run up to the 2002 Presidential elections, known and suspected opposition party members were targeted by the ruling party ZANU PF supporters (Solidarity Peace Trust 2008).

In general, since 2000 major political events such as elections, the referendum and constitutional consultative workshops were done. Sanctioned campaigns of violence mainly targeted against perceived, real supporters and sympathizers of the opposition. This violence pioneered the role youths, war veterans and trained militia play in perpetrating violence, intimidation and rape. This was done in the name of defending the nation from “Western influence” thereby planting the seed of political polarization, (Zimbabwe Peace Project 2008). In 2002, Zimbabwe was suspended from the Commonwealth of Nations on charges of human rights violations during the violent and chaotic land reform process. In addition, the 2002 presidential elections were followed by a government-sanctioned campaign of violence targeted against known and perceived opposition supporters. The same tone of violence marked the 2005 elections that were also mired in accusations of vote rigging, violence and intimidation (ZPP 2008).

The worst form of political violence was witnessed following the harmonized elections of March 2008. The government unleashed violence on defenceless citizens in retribution for the March 29 plebiscite that upset ZANU PF's majority in the House of Assembly for the first time since independence. Murders, intimidation, assaults, abductions, enforced disappearances, displacements, arbitrary arrests and detentions, torture and destruction of property preceded the run-up to the 27 June Presidential run-off election. It ended up being a one-man election as the MDC-T leader Morgan Tsvangirai pulled out citing gross violations of human rights. SADC and the AU as well as international observers condemned this election as not representing the will of the people. The violence led to more than 200 deaths, thousands were wounded and many others displaced (Zimbabwe Peace Project 2008).

In the March 2008 harmonized elections the political environment was relatively calm, but after the stalemate in the Presidential elections political tension worsened. It was caused by the Zimbabwe Electoral Commission's delay with electoral results. During the run up to the June presidential runoff elections Zimbabwe experienced intense violence which was the worst in Zimbabwe's election history. ZANU PF and its supporters mainly youths launched a crackdown on the opposition party MDC in an operation known as 'wakavhotera ani', (whom do you vote for). According to the Solidarity Peace Trust (2008) one thousand one hundred and seventy five incidences of political violence were recorded in the run up to the 2008 elections.

A lot of people had to flee their homes in search of safety mainly at churches and urban areas where the violence was low as compared to rural areas. After the annunciation of Robert Mugabe as the winner of the 2008 June run-off elections, cases of violence dropped across the country. The ruling party supporters who were the main perpetrators of the violence celebrated their victory against MDC T (Sachikonye 2011). However, this did not end the violence but political situation calmed at the formation of Government of National Unity until 31 July 2013. After elections ZANU PF had a landslide victory in which opposition members argue that elections were rigged. Therefore, the thrust of this research is to explore effectiveness of electoral processes and youths participation because most political violence emanate during and after elections.

Zimbabwe Electoral Commission is an independent electoral Board mandated to run and facilitate democratic free, fair and credible elections in Zimbabwe. The electoral process comprises of a number of stages which cascade to an election. These stages should be accessible to all citizens to ensure credible and democratic elections. However, the objective to ensure accessibility to the electoral process remains unachievable, (Zimbabwe Electoral Support Network 2010). International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES) (2010) indicates that the challenges faced by the youths to fairly access the electoral process are extensive and common in developing countries. It has emerged also from a research by the same that, there is still need for a collaborative work by the governments and the election management bodies to focus on removing barriers and stereo-types in elections. It has been suggested that lack of electoral participation is forcing youths to be involved in intra and inter party violence.

The Concept of Participation in Electoral Processes

The BRIDGE project (2010) quotes Abraham Lincoln as he views democracy as a “government of the people, by the people, for the people.” This assertion portrays a full participation and involvement of “the people” in order to achieve democracy. It is further argued that a system of government owes its legitimacy to the role that its citizens play in its election and the carrying out of its duties. Thus election requires citizen participation which is embedded in democracy.

Putnam (2010) argued that when a person does not vote that one individual citizen does not participate in the electoral process and if no one would vote democracy would end. Democracy by its very nature needs the participation of the people; without that there is no democracy. However, when one does not cast a vote it does not mean that voter still does not influence the election as much as any other voter. It still counts, as a vote against democracy. Putnam (2010) further relates democracy with high level of participation as he argues that “any situation which results in high participation by members of a group normally has high potential for democracy”. Therefore, enhancing youth’s participation in elections is a way of creating a democratic society.

There are many conventions which give youths and children the right to participate in governance. These conventions formed the basis of international frameworks on youth participation in electoral processes of their governments. Many countries are signatories and have ratified these conventions including Zimbabwe. Some of the conventions include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) Article 21 which codified everyone’s “right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through free chosen representatives (Danielle and Daniela (2011). However, given the low involvement of youth in governance issues indicates that governments which are signatories are hypocrites. In Zimbabwe, the government formed the Ministry of Youths, Indigenization and Economic Empowerment aimed at empowering youths on all spheres of governance. Despite the formation of relevant youth ministry the level of youth participation in Zimbabwe and Africa at large is trailing behind that of Western countries. Therefore, the gap between international conventions, formation of youth ministries and low youth turnout in electoral processes needs to be closed by this research.

The United Nations’ Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), the most widely ratified international agreement, has affirmed various civil and political rights for all individuals up to 18 years of age, such as the right to participate. “States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child” (Article 12). In 1996, the UN General Assembly adopted the World Programme of Action for Youth to the Year 2000 and beyond, which is still an international benchmark document concerning youths. Priority 10 is concerned with the “full and effective participation of youth in the life of society and in decision-making”.

In 2006; the African Union passed the African Youth Charter. Article 11 on youth participation specifies that every young person has the right to participate in all spheres of society. States parties agreed to: "Guarantee the participation of youth in parliament and other decision-making bodies in accordance with the prescribed laws; Facilitate the creation or strengthening of platforms for youth participation in decision-making at local, national, regional, and continental levels of governance," (Danielle and Daniela 2011).

The above conventions gave a leeway of youths' involvement in governance issues and many countries in Africa and SADC region are signatories. However, the level of youth's participation in local politics varies with the system of governance in the country. Therefore, it is empirical to research on the participation of youths in Zimbabwe in the electoral processes.

Theoretical Framework

To better understand issues of youth participation in electoral processes, the paper uses the Rational Choice Theory. The chief proponent of the rational choice theory is William Riker, who applied economics and theoretical approaches to develop complex models of politics into simple political concepts. In the theory of political coalitions, Riker (1962) demonstrated by mathematical reasoning why and how politicians form alliances. Riker and his followers applied this version of rational choice theory which they variously called rational choice, public choice, social choice, formal modelling, or positive political theory. This was to explain almost everything in political science, including voting, legislation, wars, and bureaucracy, (Scott 2000).

The basic idea of Rational Choice Theory is that patterns of behaviour in societies reflect the choices made by individuals to shape communities for their benefit. Scott (2000) notes that people make decisions about how they should act by comparing the costs and benefits of different courses of action. Furthermore, people cannot make decisions that affect the future of their societies rather they choose what is to their advantage. Rational Choice Theory identified two major explanatory factors; politicians are endlessly opportunistic and all decisions are influenced by some type of institutional setting and that political institutions structures the opportunities available to politicians and thus help to explain their actions.

This theory has been found to be applicable because an election requires one to make an informed decision. Furthermore, in making informed decisions a lot of factors can influence the electoral decision particularly on youths hence having a ripple effect on their participation. According to Gyampo and Debra (2013), The Rational Choice model stresses the importance of 'issue-based voting' and suggests that parties can influence youth's electoral performance significantly by reshaping their policies summarized in their manifestos and ideologies. However, the weakness of this theory as noted by Gyampo et al (2013) is that it abstract an individual voter from his or her social and cultural background. Hence, socio-cultural factors have got an influence in the youth's participation in electoral processes.

The Rational Choice Theory was useful in the study of the youth in Makokoba. It facilitated a clear understanding of their voting patterns. In some instances youths are failing to make informed decisions during elections because they are influenced most in their political parties. This concurred with the tenets of the theory that politicians are endless opportunistic and all decisions are influenced by some type of institutional settings. Hence, the study found out that youths are influenced by the party ideology they get from youth league institutions. Furthermore, youths are also influenced by empty sloganeering full of unmet promises, thus from a cost and benefit perspective enshrined in the theory, youths are blinkered. However, it is not only the influence they get from their political parties which affect electoral decision but also the electoral system. Youths need to be educated about the electoral processes in Zimbabwe, issues of transferring from one

constituent to the other and the registration in the voters roll should embrace the modern technology.

Research Methodology

A qualitative research methodology was used to explore how youths participate in electoral processes in Makokoba suburb. We considered a qualitative approach in this particular study, as it gives in-depth understanding of people's lived experiences, (Marshall 1996). Furthermore Moraity (2011) posits that the utmost flexibility of the approach also influences the flexibility of data collection methods .e.g. verbatim and observable. Therefore, since the study concerns itself with experiences which are difficult to quantify in numerical terms the qualitative approach is appropriate and more effective in this particular study.

It should also be put into consideration that the qualitative approach creates a synergy among participants as their responses build upon each other's comments there by creating a firm foundation for the study to be built on. Furthermore, one should be mindful of the fact that a qualitative approach is both an interpretive and naturalistic approach (Hancock 2009); therefore it allows the participants to be assessed in their natural setting thus this builds confidence and rapport within participants.

In this study we used the case study design as we sought to explore and describe the in-depth experiences of a community. Furthermore, Stake (2006) posits that in a qualitative study it is of essence to employ a case study approach if human behaviour is the gist of the study. Hence in the light of this assertion it should be considered that the study concerns itself with the participation of youths in electoral processes. The employment of a case study approach can be further justified on holistic grounds, as it encompasses an exploratory, explanatory as well as the descriptive dimension which has the ability to contribute to the comprehensiveness of the study.

Baxter and Jack (2008) posit that the case study design ought to be applauded in the field of qualitative research as it examines a phenomenon within its context. Thus from this school of thought one might argue that it ultimately promotes efficiency of data generation procedures as it allows for participants to be assessed within the context of their day to day life experiences and in their natural setting, hence it ultimately benefits both respondent and researcher as far as data generation is concerned.

Yin (2014) postulates that the case study design is an effective approach in a study that seeks to address the "how" and "why" questions. Hence in the light of this assertion the case study approach suits this particular study as it seeks investigate "how" youth participate in electoral processes and "why" they participate in the manner they do. Be that as it may be, it should also be put into consideration that a case study design seeks to fully explore a social phenomenon and institutions attached to that particular phenomenon either directly or indirectly. Furthermore, Yin (2014) appreciates the case study design as he asserts that it promotes a variegated approach to data generation as it heavily relies on multiple sources for data, thus promoting triangulation as various data collection methods will be employed which include questionnaires, interviews and questerviews. Thus, the case study approach was appropriate for this particular research because Makokoba Constituency provided lenses into the electoral processes and youth participation in Zimbabwe at large. Makokoba constituency is a hotbed of political activities in Bulawayo. Most of the political violence and demonstration start in Makokoba. Political parties take turns in winning the constituency in national elections and that shows the political composition of the constituency. Most of youths who are unemployed reside in the constituency and it is highly polarized. Makokoba Constituency was treated as a microcosm of the macrocosm.

We used a judgmental approach that identified participants with specific characteristics that are of research interest. Judgmental sampling was appropriate to this study because we wanted respondents with specific information on electoral processes. In this study we purposively selected 70 youths comprising 35 males and 35 females who formed the sample. Those who are actively involved in politics who are known to be leaders in their party formed the sample. Particularly the sample was drawn from youths both male and female residents of Makokoba Constituency. However, only 65 turned up to participate as five females did not come for unknown reasons.

Interviews and focus group discussions were used to gather primary data. Document analysis was used to collect secondary information to augment primary data. We had five focus group discussions comprising of ten people. Given that the focus groups consisted of ten people, the researcher held five group discussions with 50 different youths. The rest 15 were engaged in in-depth interviews. Information gathered was recorded in a notebook in point form exactly as the participants said. Direct observations were also recorded in a note book.

Data collected from the field was presented in a thematic way in which the researchers formulated themes or subtopics. This systematic, technique was used to encompass many words of the text into fewer content categories. Content analysis was used by the researcher to analyze the interviews, face to face interviews and the focus group discussions. Content analysis is a systematic research method for analyzing textual information in a standardized way that allows evaluators to make inferences about that information. Content analysis in this research was an essentialist and realist method which reported experiences, meanings and the reality of participants. It was a constructionist method, which examined the ways in which events, realities, experiences and routines of discourses are operating within the constituency.

Emerging Issues on Youth Participation in Electoral Processes in Makokoba

The Makokoba case shows that all is not well in the area as far as youth participation in elections is concerned. The challenges faced by the youth include lack of adequate knowledge about election processes, exploitation by politicians and shortcomings in electoral systems.

Focus Group Discussions and face to face interviews revealed that most of the youths have little knowledge on the whole process of elections. The majority of respondents demonstrated that they had little knowledge of the basic election expectations and processes. In Zimbabwe the electoral process incorporates the delimitation of boundaries, voter registration, nomination of candidates, voter education, accreditation of observers, voting and counting of votes. Most of them were not aware of the need for confirming the existence of their names in the voters' role before elections. This is a requirement they cannot afford to ignore since in Zimbabwe one is only eligible to participate in the electoral process if he or she is a registered voter.

On the election date one is required to produce citizenship identity documents (I.D) in the form of National I.D or a valid passport. Upon production of required documents, one can cast his or her vote. Most youths complained that national I.Ds cannot easily be accessed due to many requirements. Therefore, for one to be able to participate in election the government should make it easier to get a national I.D. Furthermore, youths indicated that they are not allowed to put on their Political Party regalia near the polling station. A few youths interviewed displayed knowledge about electoral processes.

The information gathered revealed that youths' knowledge about electoral process in Zimbabwe and Makokoba in particular is scant. Zimbabwe electoral process starts from citizenship registration. ZESN (2010) considers voter education as imperative in the conduct of democratic elections and that citizens should be informed in order to make rational decisions. A closer analysis of the responses

has shown that youths do not know the role of citizenship registration in the electoral process. In Zimbabwe one is eligible to participate in electoral process if he or she is a registered citizen. It is important to note that youths are not aware that voter registration is open every day during working days even if there are no elections to be held. Zimbabwe Electoral Act stipulates that voter registration is open to everyone at the offices of the Constituency Registrar any working day.

During a Focus Group Discussion one of the participants revealed that in July 2013 elections, she was a first time voter. She stated that she was directionless in the ballot box and was assisted by election officials at the polling station. However, surprising is that she completed Ordinary level in 2012 and was not able to cast her ballot. This cannot be blamed on the youth but to school curriculum and policy makers who do not consider teaching youths how to vote before they reach voting age. A comparative approach shows that in United States of America a mock polling station is prepared and youths below voting age would be seen going to cast their votes so that when they reach voting age they will know how to vote (IDEA, 2010). This serves to indicate that voter education in Makokoba and Zimbabwe at large should be taken serious. Albeit, ZEC officials in an interview confirmed that civic voter education is needed to citizens but financial capacity and human resource has always been a major stumbling block. ZEC will end up accrediting civic organisations to assist in distributing electoral information because to do it themselves is cumbersome and costly.

A combination of factors militates against meaningful participation of young people in elections in Makokoba. Youths indicated that they have well-structured system in their respective political parties. About half of youths said that they have senior positions in Youth Leagues of their parties in which they mobilize support of their respective parties. In addition, they claim to be the backbone of their political parties that run all rallies as per the orders from Youth League Administrators. It was disclosed by youths that they also provide discipline to those who do not follow party ideologies. In Makokoba, the purpose of door to door campaigns forcing people to attend rallies is done by youths so that people would be taught party ideology. In line with the above, data gathered from Chronicle Newspaper of 2 June 2015 confirms that youths are involved in campaigning for their party candidates. *“ZANU PF youths in Makokoba constituency have embarked on road shows in four Districts to canvas support for party candidate ... ahead of June 10 by election”*.

A closer analysis of the above data reveal that youths in their respective political parties are vibrantly participating in youth structures such as youth leagues in mobilizing support in rallies, door to door and road-show campaigns. Given the fact that, electoral campaign is part of electoral processes in Zimbabwe, one is bound to agree that youths are participating in the electoral process. Data collected from Focus Group Discussion shows that few of youths are appointed as electoral agents by their candidates during elections. This is a positive step towards involving youths in the electoral process but however, not all youths are appointed to be electoral agents but only few who are favoured.

Be that as it may, a closer scrutiny of youth participation in Makokoba has shown that youths are actively involved in political party programmes as compared to national electoral processes. Zimbabwean youths would benefit from the creation of platforms for electoral education for instance IEC (2014), states that in South Africa the Electoral Commission established a National Youth Dialogue on Electoral Democracy. This was a forum for youths to voice their concerns and opinions, as a result elections dates were changed so that they cannot coincide with school days to enable youths to vote. Furthermore, political parties such as ANC changed campaign message to accommodate and promise to address youth's plight. In Zimbabwe the Electoral Board has never had such initiatives to engage youths, thus the youths do not have a platform to be informed about elections so that they can make Rational Choices. Therefore, it can be viewed that in Makokoba and Zimbabwe at large youths are actively involved in their respective political party politics than in

national electoral processes. Data gathered from both interviews and focus group discussions with reference to July 2013 elections showed a variation between males and females in terms of levels and reasons for participation. The responses are presented in table 1 on the following page.

Table 1- Participation of Youth in Electoral Processes

Category	Percentage	Reasons for participation
Male youths who participated and voted	47%	-ensure party win -they were youth leaders -were electoral observers
Male youths who did not vote	5%	-only participated in campaigning -names not in voters roll -do not have national identity cards -fear of violence -were in diasporas
Female youths participated and voted	43%	-ensure party win -were youth leaders -had been promised lucrative projects -were electoral observers
Female youths who did not participate	5%	-fear of violence -not interested in politics -was out of the country -was not in the constituency -names not found in voters roll.

The above table shows that male youths are more active in political processes than females. Furthermore those youths, who participated in July, 2013 elections gave reasons that they were in youth leadership, had been promised income generating projects and were appointed as electoral observers. The reasons show that, youths generally participated for personal gains. Youths who did not participate were affected by electoral system for example the process was not accommodative to those in Diasporas, away from their constituency. Some names were not found in voters' roll. Some of the youths blamed lack of participation on their fear of violence, with some claiming that nothing was done to the perpetrators of the violence. A combination of factors can therefore be blamed for creating hurdles to the meaningful participation of young people in elections.

The analysis of data gathered revealed that, political parties' 2013 Electoral Manifestos are not all inclusive of youth affairs rather youths affairs has been stated in passing. For instance, both ZANU PF and MDC-T manifestos stated the creation of jobs for youths without showing how. However, the loyal and tireless support rendered by youths to their parties as indicated from data collected, it would be noble for political parties to include a section in their Manifestos which discuss at length the future of youths after elections. The absence of youth centered sections in Manifestos proved that youths are used by political parties to win election. Ransford and Debra (2013) note that; in Ghana electoral outcomes are abound but little has been written about the contributions of party manifestos to shaping the electoral behavior of the youths. They further notes that parties did not do much to inform their young supporters of the contents of their manifestos.

Another observation is that youths are used in unlawful activities for instance being bused to cause mayhem in different parts of the country. This concurs with Dodo's (2012) observation, that youths were ferried from Harare to Bindura for campaigning purposes. An analysis of door to door and road-show campaigns in which the youth are involved in can be viewed as source violence. It can be argued from the findings that youths are not making rational informed decisions. Furthermore,

active participation of Makokoba youths in their parties during elections and the level of their involvement in governance after elections do not tally. This led to an analytical conclusion that youths are used by party candidates to win an election and after that nothing will be done for them. In Kenya, Youths only participate in political activities when KANU recruited them into the KANU Youth Wingers, an unstructured organization composed of stone throwers, hecklers, and youth engaged in anti-social behavior, (Imoite 2007).

It has been discovered from the research that for one to be eligible for elections should produce a national identity card and registered as a voter. Therefore, electoral process in Zimbabwe starts with citizenship registration. The process of citizenship registration is laborious as the requirements are too much and one should have a clear birth record to obtain a national identity card. Some youths interviewed indicated that they are failing to participate in elections because they do not have national identity cards. Reasons raised were that both parents were dead hence no one can stand on their behalf in the boring process. Others indicated that birth records and certificates were lost, destroyed by fire and other accident, however, the registry offices no longer have records because their old system of filing is no longer used. ZESN (2008) concurred that the birth certificate is a core requirement yet difficult to obtain; specifically the "long" birth certificate for one to be considered a citizen. Anyone with a short birth certificate is now required to get the long version before they can get an identity document.

ZESN (2010) notes that, the law provides that for one to register as a voter, they present at the relevant offices that is, the Constituency Registrar and may produce proof of residence and their national identity document. They complete the necessary documents and receive a certificate of registration. However, while proof of resident as a requirement is restricting youth's participation in elections. Some youths in Makokoba states that they are tenants while landlords are away in rural area hence they cannot bother themselves for such requirements rather they don't participate to avoid the hustles. Furthermore, some youths decried on time frame given for voter registration is too minimal, in most cases the electoral commission opens for registrations few months towards elections. Be that as it may, voter registration exercise should be done anytime towards or after elections. However, the commission give reasons of lack of resources financially and human capital.

Youths indicated that they are mobile that means they can change constituency at any time. In such a scenario, they are required to visit ZEC offices so that their names can be shifted to their respective constituency and obtain a voter slip. Given the fact that one has to visit the offices is time consuming and at times after visiting official can give you another date. In the same vein, others states that during elections they do not vote because they will be in Diaspora such as in South Africa and Botswana. Hence they pleaded that if the government can pave way for on line voting or Diaspora voting then they can be able to fully participate in elections. Hence one is bound to agree with the Rational Choice Theory that decisions are influenced by some type of institutional setting and behavior which can affect people's choice. After registering as a voter one is given a voter certificate in form of a slip. Some youths states that they failed to vote in 2013 because they misplaced the slips and their names were yet to be in the voters roll hence those slips were a pass for them to vote. The ZHRC (2013) noted that the reports of arrests of people with fake voter registration slips presents a possibility of a large scale use of these fake documents.

Most of the youths suggested that it would be easy for them to participate in electoral processes if the processes would be done online. Taking for instance, voter registration they point out that once one got his or her national identity card should be automatically enter in the voter's roll. Changing of constituency and being out of the country during elections should not affect their electoral participation if the electoral commission adopts on-line or e-electoral processes. Youths suggest that government should move with time because most of them are well versed on how to use modern

technology such as internet and that can be an opportunity to include them in electoral processes. Hence, they regard the current system as too old and as a stumbling block in their involvement in elections in Zimbabwe.

Conclusion

The research revealed that a lot needs to be done in order for youths to participate in national elections. It is important to have some educational workshops or national youth dialogues on elections. Youths should also desist from employing door to door campaign because they end up igniting electoral violence. The level of participation of youths in their political parties should be elevated to national elections. Youths should utilize their right to participate in governance as enshrined in international, regional and national frameworks. The research summed up that youths are actively involved in political party politics. This gives a window for them to be used by individuals for personal gains. Youths are the future of Zimbabwe, Africa and the world at large hence they should be involved in national elections. Peace and good governance can be necessitated by effective youth involvement rather than passive participation.

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